

3rd Joint AITVM-STVM Conference

From 21st to 24th
MAY 2024

Association of Institutions for
Tropical Veterinary Medicine

Society of Tropical Veterinary Medicine

Le **CORUM**
Conference Center
Montpellier
FRANCE

TROPICAL VETERINARY MEDICINE
IN CHALLENGING TIMES

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Unravelling the socioeconomic factors linked to antibiotic use in poultry farms: a qualitative study in the Analamanga region, Madagascar

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Introduction:

Antimicrobial resistance is a global public health threat mainly caused by the massive use and misuse of antimicrobials. Addressing the animal health part of this issue is challenging in low-and-middle-income countries where information is scarce regarding access and use of veterinary drugs. Our objective was therefore to investigate the socio-economic factors of antibiotic use in poultry farms of Madagascar.

Methods:

We conducted semi-structured interviews with 79 poultry farmers in the Analamanga region in April 2023. Thematic analysis was used to extract the perceptions and practices related to veterinary care, the supply and uses of veterinary medicines.

Results & Discussion:

The majority of poultry farmers had received little livestock training and raised poultry as a side job. Most farmers had very basic knowledge of diseases and treatments. They relied on varied sources of advice for how to take care of poultry: feed/chicks/drug suppliers, technicians, veterinarians, other farmers and family members in decreasing order. Access to veterinary drugs was easy, without prior clinical examination and without prescriptions. Vitamins and antibiotics were the most commonly used medication. Many constraints (food price, quality of inputs, poor selling conditions) limited the financial capacity of farmers to invest in good practices (hygiene, disinfection, vaccination...). Farmers tended to agree with the idea of using fewer antibiotics in the future but this was mainly driven by the prospect of reducing costs than of preserving public health. In conclusion, good antibiotic use should be promoted through feed/chicks/drug suppliers to maximize efficiency in contexts of poor farmers' professionalization.